

**ADJECTIVES-DEFINITION, FORMS, TYPES, USAGE AND
EXAMPLES**

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***Abstract:** In this scientific article, the types, levels, definition of quality are given, several examples are given. That is, there is a lot of information about quality.*

***Keywords:** adjective, example, levels, pronoun, Cambridge, Oxford Learner, degree of comparison, types of adjective.*

INTRODUCTION.

What Is an Adjective?

An adjective is a part of speech that can be used to describe or provide more information about a noun or pronoun that acts as the subject in a sentence. Adjectives are found after the verb or before the noun it modifies.

Definition of an Adjective

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, an adjective is defined as “a word that describes a noun or pronoun.” The Collins Dictionary gives a more elaborate definition. According to it, “an adjective is a word such as ‘big’, ‘dead’, or ‘financial’ that describes a person or thing, or gives extra information about them. Adjectives usually come before nouns or after link verbs.”

The Oxford Learner’s Dictionary defines an adjective as “a word that describes a person or thing, for example ‘big’, ‘red’ and ‘clever’ in a big house, red wine and a clever idea.” An adjective is “a word belonging to one of the major

form classes in any of numerous languages and typically serving as a modifier of a noun to denote a quality of the thing named, to indicate its quantity or extent, or to specify a thing as distinct from something else”, according to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary.

THE MAIN PART.

Forms of Adjectives – Degrees of Comparison

Did you know that adjectives can be used to compare similar qualities of different subjects that perform the same action. There are three forms of adjectives or rather three degrees of comparison. They are:

- Positive or Absolute Form
- Comparative Form
- Superlative Form

Positive Degree of Comparison:

The positive form or the positive degree of comparison is the form of the adjective used in the original form. For example: This book is interesting. This form of adjective is used when there is no other subject to be compared.

Comparative Degree of Comparison

The comparative form of the adjective is used when two subjects performing the same action or possessing the same quality are compared. For example: The book I read yesterday was more interesting than the one I read today.

Superlative Degree of Comparison

The superlative degree of comparison is used when comparing the same quality of two or more subjects and to represent that a subject is superior to two or more subjects in performing an action. For example: This fantasy novel is the most interesting book that I have ever read.

Types of Adjectives

Adjectives can be divided into different categories based on their functions when used in a sentence. The different types of adjectives are:

- Possessive Adjectives
- Interrogative Adjectives
- Demonstrative Adjectives
- Compound Adjectives
- Possessive Adjectives:

These adjectives, like possessive pronouns, are used to show or represent possession of a quality. For example: my, your, his, her, their, its, whose, etc.

Interrogative Adjectives:

An adjective that is used to modify a noun or a pronoun by asking a question is called an interrogative adjective. There are only a few adjectives that can be termed as interrogative adjectives. They are whose, what and which.

Demonstrative Adjectives:

Demonstrative adjectives are mainly used to describe the position of a subject (a noun or pronoun) in space or time. This, that, these and those are the demonstrative adjectives in English.

Compound Adjectives:

Compound adjectives consist of two or more adjectives that are combined together to form an adjective that can be used to modify the subject. Some examples of compound adjectives are cotton-tailed, curly-haired, absent-minded, happy-go-lucky, etc.

How to Use Adjectives in Sentences?

Adjectives are known to give your writing and speech a very flowery look. It aids in making it descriptive and also in giving your readers and listeners a visual treat. However, stuffing it with too many adjectives can make it look or sound

vague and unclear. This would only lead to misunderstanding of your content. Knowing when, where and how to use adjectives is a skill that you should master.

CONCLUSION

Any piece of writing should be clear and precise. Find out if there is a word that specifically means whatever you are trying to convey. For example: quick, swift, hasty, fleet, etc. are all adjectives that mean 'very fast'. Likewise, contented, cheerful, merry, joyful, ecstatic, delighted, etc. are all words that describe different degrees of happiness. There is also another concept that you should know. There is a particular order in which you should place adjectives when you are using two or more adjectives to describe the same subject or object.

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